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Research Paper

Development and Validation of Stability-Indicating RP-HPLC Method for the Determination of Imeglimin Hydrochloride in Bulk Form

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ABSTRACT

Background: Imeglimin, a novel oral antidiabetic agent belonging to the tetrahydrotriazine class, is widely used for the management of Type 2 diabetes mellitus. The present study aimed to develop and validate a stability-indicating reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatographic (RP-HPLC) method for the quantitative estimation of Imeglimin Hydrochloride in bulk form. A simple, efficient, accurate, precise, and reproducible analytical method was successfully established. Chromatographic separation was carried out using an RP-HPLC system equipped with a C18 column (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size), ensuring optimal resolution and peak symmetry. The mobile phase consisted of a buffer solution prepared by dissolving 0.6306 g of ammonium formate in HPLC-grade water, with the pH adjusted to 4.0 using dilute formic acid, along with methanol as the organic phase. The developed method demonstrated suitability for routine analysis and stability studies of Imeglimin Hydrochloride. **Results:** The retention time for Imeglimin Hydrochloride was determined to be 2.594 minutes, with strong absorbance sensitivity observed at a wavelength of 240 nm. The linear regression analysis yielded the equation ($y = 21372x + 6E+06$) with a correlation coefficient $R^2 = 0.9981$ indicating an excellent linear relationship. **Conclusion:** The developed RP-HPLC method for the estimation of Imeglimin Hydrochloride was found to be linear, precise, accurate, specific, selective, and highly reliable. The method exhibited consistent performance, making it suitable for routine pharmaceutical analysis and quality control of the drug, thereby ensuring its

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safety, efficacy, and purity. All validation parameters were evaluated in accordance with ICH guidelines, including specificity, linearity, precision, accuracy, robustness, limit of detection (LOD), and limit of quantification (LOQ). The results obtained for all these parameters were within the acceptable limits, confirming the suitability and robustness of the proposed analytical method for its intended purpose.

INTRODUCTION

Rapid economic growth and urbanization have significantly contributed to the rising global burden of diabetes. Changes in lifestyle, including sedentary behaviour, unhealthy dietary habits, and increased stress levels, have led to higher prevalence rates. Additionally, improved life expectancy and population aging further add to the growing number of diabetes cases worldwide, making it a major public health challenge [1]. The rising prevalence of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) poses a significant global public health challenge [2,3]. Despite substantial efforts by governmental and non-governmental organizations toward its diagnosis, treatment, prevention, and awareness, the incidence continues to increase. This upward trend is particularly evident among older adults, individuals with obesity, and high-risk ethnic population [4]. Over recent decades, type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) has become increasingly widespread, paralleling the rise in key risk factors such as metabolic dysfunction, obesity, and sedentary lifestyles. Rapid urbanization, unhealthy dietary patterns, reduced physical activity, and increasing stress levels have further accelerated this trend. Additionally, aging populations and genetic predisposition contribute to the growing burden, making T2DM a significant and escalating global health concern [5], [6], [7]. Several oral antidiabetic agents are available for managing the complex pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes mellitus; however, each therapeutic class is associated with inherent limitations [8]. Many of these drugs are linked to notable adverse effects,

such as urinary tract infections with sodium–glucose cotransporter-2 (SGLT2) inhibitors (e.g., dapagliflozin); weight gain with sulfonylureas like glipizide; hypoglycemia with sulfonylureas (e.g., glibenclamide), meglitinides, thiazolidinediones, GLP-1 receptor agonists, and insulin; edema with thiazolidinediones such as pioglitazone; and an increased risk of pancreatitis with GLP-1 receptor agonists [9]. Additionally, issues such as declining efficacy over time, patient non-compliance, and cost burden further limit optimal disease management. Despite the wide array of available therapies, none adequately address all three fundamental components of T2DM pathophysiology—excessive hepatic glucose production due to gluconeogenesis, increased insulin resistance, and impaired insulin secretion resulting from pancreatic β -cell dysfunction [10]. Imeglimin is a novel oral antidiabetic agent belonging to the tetrahydrotriazine class, developed for the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) [11]. It is marketed under the brand name Twymeeg [12] and received its first regulatory approval for clinical use in Japan in June 2021, marking a significant advancement in diabetes therapeutics [13]. Notably, imeglimin represents the first approved drug of the emerging “glimin” class of glucose-lowering agents, introducing a new pharmacological category distinct from existing antidiabetic therapies [14]. The mechanism of action of imeglimin is multifaceted and targets the core pathophysiological defects of T2DM. It enhances Glucose-Stimulated Insulin Secretion (GSIS) from pancreatic β -cells in a glucose-dependent manner, thereby reducing the risk of hypoglycemia. Additionally, imeglimin has been shown to preserve and potentially restore pancreatic β -cell mass and function, which are progressively impaired in patients with T2DM. Furthermore, it improves insulin sensitivity in peripheral tissues, particularly in the liver and skeletal muscle,

leading to enhanced glucose uptake and reduced hepatic glucose production.

Imeglimin also exerts beneficial effects on mitochondrial function by improving mitochondrial bioenergetics and reducing oxidative stress, which are critical contributors to insulin resistance and β -cell dysfunction. Through these combined actions—enhancing insulin secretion, preserving β -cell integrity, improving insulin sensitivity, and modulating mitochondrial pathways—imeglimin helps restore overall glucose homeostasis. This unique and comprehensive mechanism distinguishes it from traditional antidiabetic agents and highlights its potential as an effective therapeutic option for the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus [11-14].

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1. DRUG PROFILE:

The structure of Imeglimin Hydrochloride is:

Imeglimin Hydrochloride is classified as an antidiabetic agent used in the management of Type 2 diabetes mellitus. Its chemical name is (R)-6-imino-N,N,4-trimethyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazin-2-amine hydrochloride. The molecular formula is $C_6H_{14}ClN_5$, with a molecular weight of 191.66 g/mol. For the present study, Imeglimin Hydrochloride was procured from Enaltec Laboratories.

2.2. METHOD:

2.2.1 INITIALISATION OF RP-HPLC METHOD

Table 1: Solubility of Imeglimin HCl in different solvents.

Solvents	Solubility
Water	Freely soluble
Methanol	Soluble
Acetonitrile	Soluble
Acetone	Soluble
Chloroform	Slightly soluble
0.1M NaOH	Sparingly soluble

The solubility of the Imeglimin Hydrochloride active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) was systematically evaluated in a range of solvents, including water, acetonitrile, methanol, ethanol, acetone, water–acetonitrile mixtures, orthophosphoric acid, OPA–acetonitrile buffer, and water–methanol mixtures, as summarized in Table 1. This comprehensive assessment was carried out to identify the most suitable solvent system for effective chromatographic analysis. The results indicated that Imeglimin Hydrochloride exhibited better solubility in polar solvents, particularly methanol and HPLC-grade water. Based on these findings, a combination of methanol and HPLC-grade water was selected as the mobile phase. This selection was further supported by their widespread availability, compatibility with the RP-HPLC system, low toxicity, and cost-effectiveness, making them ideal for routine analytical applications and method development.

Preparation of Mobile Phase

A precisely weighed quantity of 0.6306 g of ammonium formate was dissolved in 1000 mL of HPLC-grade water to prepare the buffer solution. The pH was carefully adjusted to 4.0 using dilute formic acid. The prepared solution was mixed thoroughly to ensure complete dissolution, followed by sonication to remove any dissolved

gases. Finally, the solution was filtered to obtain a clear buffer suitable for chromatographic analysis.

Mobile Phase A: Buffer Solution

Mobile Phase B: Methanol was used as the second Mobile Phase.

Preparation of diluent

A diluent was prepared by mixing HPLC-grade water and acetonitrile in the ratio of 900:100 (v/v). This solution was used both as the diluent for sample preparation and as the blank during analysis.

Preparation of standard stock solution

A standard stock solution of Imeglimin Hydrochloride (2000 ppm) was prepared by accurately weighing 200 mg of the active pharmaceutical ingredient and transferring it into a 100 mL volumetric flask. Approximately 15 mL of the prepared diluent was added to dissolve the drug, and the mixture was thoroughly shaken to ensure uniform dispersion. The solution was then sonicated for about 10 minutes to achieve complete dissolution of the drug. After ensuring clarity, the volume was made up to the mark with the same diluent, resulting in a homogeneous standard stock solution suitable for further analysis.

Preparation of standard solution

A 1000 ppm standard solution of Imeglimin Hydrochloride was prepared by accurately transferring 10 mL of the previously prepared standard stock solution into a 20 mL volumetric flask. About 5 mL of the diluent was added, and the solution was sonicated for approximately 10 minutes to ensure complete mixing. The final volume was then made up to the mark with the diluent, yielding a clear and homogeneous solution suitable for further analytical use.

Preparation of test solution

Test solutions of Imeglimin Hydrochloride at concentrations of 800, 900, 1000, 1100, and 1200 ppm were prepared by transferring 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12 mL, respectively, of the standard stock solution into separate 20 mL volumetric flasks. Each solution was initially diluted with about 5 mL of the diluent, sonicated for 10 minutes to ensure complete mixing, and then made up to the final volume with the same diluent.

Selection of Detection Wavelength

A solution of Imeglimin Hydrochloride was prepared using methanol as the solvent. The UV spectrum was recorded by scanning the solution over the wavelength range of 200–400 nm. The drug exhibited maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) at 240 nm, which was selected as the optimal detection wavelength for further analysis.

Chromatographic conditions

Table 2: Optimized chromatographic conditions used to validate the proposed method.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Details
1.	HPLC System Used	Agilents 1200 Series
2.	Software used	EZ chrom Elite
3.	Column	C18 (150 mm×4.6 mm, 5 μ m)
4.	Column Temperature	30°C
5.	Flow Rate	1 ml/min
6.	Injection Volume	5 μ L
7.	Wavelength	240 nm
8.	Run Time	15 min
9.	Mobile Phase	Buffer
10.	Elution Mode	Isocratic

In accordance with ICH Q2(R1) guidelines, the developed analytical method was validated for key performance characteristics, including specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, limit of detection (LOD), and limit of quantification (LOQ) [17], [18]. Validation of optimized method of Imeglimin HCl by RP-HPLC method.

3. RESULT

System Suitability:

System suitability was evaluated using a standard solution of Imeglimin Hydrochloride at a

Table 3: System Suitability Study Result of Imeglimin HCl

Parameter	Achieved Value	Acceptance
Theoretical plates	2923	> 2000
Tailing factor	1.23	≤ 2
%RSD of Area	1.02	≤ 2

Specificity:

Method specificity was assessed by injecting methanol as the blank and a 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ standard solution of Imeglimin Hydrochloride. The chromatograms showed no interfering peaks from the diluent at the retention time of the drug,

concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Key chromatographic parameters, including retention time, theoretical plates, tailing factor, and percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD), were determined to ensure the adequacy of the system. System suitability refers to a set of tests performed to verify that the chromatographic system is functioning properly before or during analysis. It ensures that the system provides acceptable performance in terms of resolution, repeatability, and efficiency, thereby confirming the reliability and accuracy of the analytical results.

thereby confirming that the method is specific for the estimation of Imeglimin Hydrochloride. Specificity is defined as the ability of an analytical method to accurately measure the analyte in the presence of other components such as impurities, degradants, or excipients, without any interference, ensuring reliable and accurate results.

Figure 1: Chromatogram for blank

Figure 2: Chromatogram for standard imeglimin

Accuracy:

The accuracy of the developed method was evaluated at five concentration levels (800, 900, 1000, 1100, and 1200 ppm), with each level analyzed in sextuplicate (six replicates) in accordance with ICH guidelines. Accuracy was determined using the standard addition method. The obtained results were within acceptable limits and were expressed in terms of standard deviation

(SD) and percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD), indicating the reliability of the method.

Accuracy is defined as the closeness of agreement between the value found and the true or accepted reference value. It reflects the trueness of the method and its ability to provide results that are free from systematic error.

Calculation of AVG. STD, %RSD of different concentration (800 PPM- 1200 PPM) of Imeglimin HCl on same day:

Table 4: Result of Accuracy of Imeglimin HCl (800-1200 PPM)

(The method pass the test and RSD was found to be less than 2%)

Sr. No.	800 PPM	900 PPM	1000 PPM	1100 PPM	1200 PPM
1	23496028	25409155	27436386	29086302	31677393
2	23265804	25248053	26997831	29393554	31496797
3	23063272	24908059	26856972	29667099	31517365
4	22885684	24731755	26807069	29791092	31749253
5	22876723	25066917	27159725	29634361	31167739
6	23148722	25101738	27074911	29819701	31853488
MEAN	23122705.5	25101738	27055482.33	29565351.5	31577005.83
SD	236956.8107	249991.048	228372.863	279202.4752	242354.6513
%RSD	1.02	1.00	0.84	0.94	0.77

Linearity:

Linearity of the developed method was established by constructing a calibration curve using five concentrations of Imeglimin Hydrochloride (800, 900, 1000, 1100, and 1200 µg/mL). Each concentration was injected into the HPLC system, and the corresponding peak responses were

recorded. The calibration curve was plotted with concentration versus peak response, and the regression equation along with the correlation coefficient was determined. The results demonstrated a strong linear relationship between concentration and peak response over the studied range.

Linearity is defined as the ability of an analytical method to produce results that are directly proportional to the concentration of the analyte within a given range, indicating the method's suitability for quantitative analysis.

Table 5: Result of Linearity of Imeglimin HCl (800-1200 PPM)

	800 PPM	900 PPM	1000 PPM	1100 PPM	1200 PPM
1	23496028	25409155	27436386	29086302	31677393
2	23265804	25248053	26997831	29393554	31496797
3	23063272	24908059	26856972	29667099	31517365
4	22885684	24731755	26807069	29791092	31749253
5	22876723	25066917	27159725	29634361	31167739
6	23148722	25101738	27074911	29819701	31853488
MEAN	23122705.5	25101738	27055482.33	29565351.5	31577005.83
SD	236956.8107	249991.048	228372.863	279202.4752	242354.6513
%RSD	1.02	1.00	0.84	0.94	0.77

PPM	AREA
800	23122705.5
900	25101738
1000	27055482.33
1100	29565351.5
1200	31577005.83

Figure 3: Linearity graph of Imeglimin HCl API

RSD value was found less than 2%. A regression coefficient (R^2) of 0.9981 obtained between the standard concentrations of Imeglimin Hydrochloride and their corresponding mean peak areas indicated excellent linearity of the calibration curve. Additional regression parameters further supported the linear behavior of the method across the concentration range of 800–

1200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, confirming its suitability for quantitative analysis.

Precision

Precision of the developed method was evaluated using Imeglimin Hydrochloride solutions at concentrations of 800, 900, 1000, 1100, and 1200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Both intraday and interday precision

studies were carried out according to the specified analytical procedures. The results demonstrated consistent and reproducible measurements across different time intervals, indicating the reliability of the method. Precision is defined as the degree of agreement among a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample under prescribed conditions. It reflects the reproducibility of the method and is commonly expressed in terms of standard deviation (SD) and percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD).

a. Repeatability

Repeatability, also known as intra-assay precision, was evaluated by analyzing Imeglimin Hydrochloride solutions in the concentration range of 800–1200 ppm. Each concentration was injected six times under identical operating conditions within the same day. The results demonstrated consistent responses, confirming the method's repeatability and short-term precision.

Repeatability is defined as the degree of agreement between independent test results obtained under the same operating conditions over a short time interval. It reflects the method's ability to produce consistent results when performed by the same analyst using the same equipment.

6 Reps of Imeglimin HCl was performed and %RSD was calculated as follows:

Table 6: Result of Repeatability Study (Intra Day) of Imeglimin HCl (800-1200 PPM)

(The method passed the test as the RSD was less than 2%)

	800 PPM	900 PPM	1000 PPM	1100 PPM	1200 PPM
1	22473511	26892041	27733123	32261604	32653839
2	22508927	26718420	27814424	31758432	32682552
3	22443523	26680231	27812520	31775303	32834887
4	22445358	26563127	27881443	31740197	32907238
5	22493119	26791505	28045012	32080530	32885915
6	22515901	26501275	28168152	31803524	32924444
MEAN	22480056.5	26691099.83	27909112.33	31903265	32814812.5
SD	31210.53973	144037.208	164683.9792	216203.6217	117834.9672
%RSD	0.14	0.54	0.59	0.68	0.36

b. Intermediate Precision

Intermediate precision of the developed method was evaluated by analyzing Imeglimin Hydrochloride solutions in the concentration range of 800–1200 ppm. Each concentration was injected six times on two different days to assess variability under normal laboratory conditions. The results demonstrated consistent performance, confirming the method's reliability across different days.

Intermediate precision is defined as the degree of agreement among test results obtained within the same laboratory under varied conditions, such as different days, analysts, or equipment. It reflects the method's reproducibility under routine analytical conditions.

DAY-1: 6 Reps of Imeglimin HCl was performed for interday precision and %RSD was calculated as follows:

Table 7: Result of Intermediate Precision (Inter Day-1) of Imeglimin HCl (The method passed the test as the RSD was less than 2%)

	800 PPM	900 PPM	1000 PPM	1100 PPM	1200 PPM
1	23496028	25409155	27436386	29086302	31677393
2	23265804	25248053	26997831	29393554	31496797
3	23063272	24908059	26856972	29667099	31517365
4	22885684	24731755	26807069	29791092	31749253
5	22876723	25066917	27159725	29634361	31167739
6	23148722	25101738	27074911	29819701	31853488
MEAN	23122705.5	25101738	27055482.33	29565351.5	31577005.83
SD	236956.8107	249991.048	228372.863	279202.4752	242354.6513
%RSD	1.02	1.00	0.84	0.94	0.77

DAY-2: 6 Reps of Imeglimin HCl was performed for interday precision and %RSD was calculated as follows:

Table 8: Result of Intermediate Precision (Inter Day-2) of Imeglimin HCl (The method passed the test as the RSD was less than 2%)

	800 PPM	900 PPM	1000 PPM	1100 PPM	1200 PPM
1	22852224	25373979	27678154	31586892	33050552
2	22963811	25260822	27696800	31516824	33077423
3	22895265	25278191	27595439	31536793	32975790
4	22857125	25122540	27621141	31542723	32985608
5	22771063	25270275	27607330	31469839	32981033
6	22836310	25219103	27721326	31407514	32958497
MEAN	22862633	25254151.67	27653365	31510097.5	33004817.17
SD	64060.10565	82208.24098	52216.51107	63029.89021	47510.19875
%RSD	0.28	0.33	0.19	0.20	0.14

c.) Reproducibility

Reproducibility of the method refers to the precision obtained when the analysis is performed under varying conditions across different laboratories. It is typically evaluated through collaborative studies to ensure the method yields consistent and comparable results irrespective of location. Reproducibility is defined as the degree

of agreement among test results obtained for the same sample when the analysis is conducted in different laboratories, using different analysts and equipment. It reflects the robustness and transferability of the analytical method for standardization purposes.

Robustness:

Table 9: Result of Robustness of Imeglimin HCl

		800 PPM	900 PPM	1000 PPM	1100 PPM	1200 PPM
Buffer	1	18349919	20764591	23713093	26580524	27778235
Conc.	2	18278858	20734015	23841333	26582398	28016411
Plus	MEAN	18314388.5	20749303	23777213	26581461	27897323
	RSD	0.27436	0.10420	0.38137	0.00499	0.60370
Buffer	1	18219925	20608894	23849045	26655666	27916723

Conc.	2	18252334	20800719	23757021	26656845	28159349
Minus	MEAN	18236129.5	20704806.5	23803033	26656255.5	28038036
	RSD	0.12567	0.65512	0.27337	0.00313	0.61189
pH Plus	1	18327107	20795818	23807436	26707729	27702075
	2	18295434	20710956	23578212	26588776	27931358
	MEAN	18311270.5	20753387	23692824	26648252.5	27816716.5
	RSD	0.12231	0.28914	0.68411	0.31564	0.58284
pH Minus	1	18328124	20811365	23757020	26815581	28122888
	2	18382655	20806631	23745530	26858607	28343244
	MEAN	18355389.5	20808998	23751275	26837094	28233066
	RSD	0.21007	0.01609	0.03421	0.11337	0.55189
Flow	1	17096813	19398557	21990498	24669757	25403521
Rate	2	17066759	19276964	22074594	24537920	25477483
Plus	MEAN	17081786	19337760.5	22032546	24603838.5	25440502
	RSD	0.12441	0.44462	0.26990	0.37890	0.20557
Flow	1	20797762	23705436	26936852	30055832	31556419
Rate	2	20819743	23539751	26888138	30105315	31624210
Minus	MEAN	20808752.5	23622593.5	26912495	30080573.5	31590314.5
	RSD	0.07469	0.49595	0.12799	0.11632	0.15174
Wavelength	1	16833334	19145700	21584595	24076560	25185027
Plus	2	16638191	18952645	21388060	24098427	25385256
	MEAN	16735762.5	19049172.5	21486327.5	24087493.5	25285141.5
	RSD	0.82450	0.71662	0.64679	0.06419	0.55995
Wavelength	1	16602392	18869569	21505893	24090973	25198420
Minus	2	16495152	18763846	21359582	24029140	25353478
	MEAN	16548772	18816707.5	21432737.5	24060056.5	25275949
	RSD	0.45822	0.39729	0.48271	0.18172	0.43378
Column	1	18646548	21247347	24110000	26909923	28224087
Temperature	2	18757019	21168285	24127590	26952923	28258745
Plus	MEAN	18701783.5	21207816	24118795	26931423	28241416
	RSD	0.41769	0.26361	0.05157	0.11290	0.08678
Column	1	18711123	21198964	24138050	26813272	28220261
Temperature	2	18576826	21086701	24341598	26816527	28242637
Minus	MEAN	18643974.5	21142832.5	24239824	26814899.5	28231449
	RSD	0.50935	0.37546	0.59378	0.00858	0.05604

Force degradation study

Forced degradation studies were conducted under four stress conditions—acidic, alkaline, oxidative (H₂O₂), and thermal—to evaluate the stability profile of Imeglimin Hydrochloride. The standard drug was subjected to these stress conditions to induce partial degradation. In accordance with ICH Q1A (R2) guidelines, the objective was to develop a stability-indicating analytical method capable of effectively separating the intact drug peak from its degradation products. These studies

also aided in identifying conditions that lead to drug instability, thereby providing essential information for developing appropriate formulation, storage, and handling strategies to ensure product stability. Forced degradation studies are defined as stress testing procedures in which a drug substance is subjected to extreme conditions to accelerate its degradation. These studies help in understanding degradation pathways, identifying degradation products, and

establishing the stability-indicating nature of an analytical method.

The detailed procedure for forced degradation is described below:

Table 10: Procedure of Force Degradation studies of Imeglimin HCl

Degradation conditions	Procedure	No. of Injections
Acidic degradation	1. Add 5 & 10 mL 0.1N HCl in mixed test solution + stand for 1 hour + neutralize with same concentration of alkali. 2. Add 5 & 10 mL 1N HCl in mixed test solution + stand for 1 hour + neutralize with same concentration of alkali.	01 injection blank 02 injection of std. solution 02 injection of test solution
Alkali degradation	1. Add 5 & 10 mL 0.1N NaOH in mixed test solution + stand for 1 hour + neutralize with same concentration of acid. 2. Add 5 & 10 mL 1N NaOH in mixed test solution + stand for 1 hour + neutralize with same concentration of acid.	01 injection blank 02 injection of std. solution 02 injection of test solution
Oxidative degradation	1. Add 5% - 5 mL and 10 mL H ₂ O ₂ 2. Add 10% - 5 mL and 10 mL H ₂ O ₂	01 injection blank 02 injection of std. solution 02 injection of test solution
Thermal degradation	Treated at increased temperature (80°C) for 24 hour.	01 injection blank 02 injection of std. solution 02 injection of test solution
Photolytic Degradation (Light)	Light exposure of sample – 24 hours	01 injection blank 02 injection of std. solution 02 injection of test solution
Photolytic Degradation (UV)	UV exposure of sample – 24 hours	01 injection blank 02 injection of std. solution 02 injection of test solution

Stability:

Standard solution samples of Imeglimin Hydrochloride were stored at room temperature to evaluate their stability over time. The experimental results indicated that, under the specified storage conditions, the drug remained stable for at least two days without any significant change in its characteristics. Stability is defined as the ability of a drug substance or solution to maintain its chemical, physical, and analytical

integrity within specified limits over a given period under defined storage conditions.

DISCUSSION

This study successfully developed and validated a novel, rapid, and efficient reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for the quantification of Imeglimin Hydrochloride. Compared to previously reported methods, the proposed approach offers significant advantages, including shorter analysis time and

reduced solvent consumption. The retention time of Imeglimin HCl (2.594 minutes) is considerably lower than earlier methods, thereby improving laboratory throughput and overall efficiency. Moreover, decreased solvent usage reduces analytical costs and supports environmentally sustainable practices in line with green analytical chemistry principles.

The method demonstrated excellent robustness, accuracy, and precision, with consistent %RSD values and full compliance with ICH validation guidelines. Linearity was established over the selected concentration range, showing a strong correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.9981$), confirming reliable quantitative performance. High specificity was also observed, with well-resolved peaks and no interference from excipients or impurities.

Overall, the developed RP-HPLC method is highly suitable for routine pharmaceutical analysis of Imeglimin HCl. Its rapid analysis, high sensitivity at 240 nm, and excellent peak resolution make it particularly effective for quality control applications and the detection of low drug concentrations, ensuring product safety and efficacy.

CONCLUSION

Agilent RP-HPLC technology was utilized to develop and validate a reliable, rapid, and efficient analytical method for the estimation of Imeglimin Hydrochloride. Although the method is simple in design, it is novel and has not been previously reported. Compared with earlier published methods, the proposed approach demonstrates superior performance, with reduced analysis time and lower solvent consumption, making it both time-efficient and cost-effective. The developed method was found to be robust, accurate, precise, and specific for the determination of Imeglimin HCl.

The procedure established for the quantification of Imeglimin API and its pharmaceutical formulation

is straightforward, rapid, and economical, as supported by the obtained statistical data. A sensitive and simple RP-HPLC method employing a PDA detector was successfully developed and validated in accordance with ICH guidelines. The method exhibited excellent compliance with all validation parameters, including robustness, accuracy, precision, linearity, specificity, and system suitability.

Furthermore, the method demonstrated reliable %RSD values, strong linearity, and excellent peak separation with enhanced resolution. These characteristics confirm its suitability for routine quality control analysis of Imeglimin Hydrochloride in pharmaceutical laboratories, ensuring consistent and accurate results.

Abbreviations

ICH	International conference on harmonization
HPLC	High performance liquid chromatography
RP-HPLC	Reversed Phase-High performance liquid chromatography
PPM	Parts Per Million
SGLT2	Sodium-glucose cotransporter-2
GLP-1	Glucagon-like peptide-1
API	Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient
OPA	Ortho Phosphoric Acid
ACN	Acetonitrile
LOQ	Limit of quantitation
LOD	Limit of detection
RSD	Relative standard deviation
SD	Standard deviation
PDA	Photo Diode Array Detector

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they don't have any conflict of interest .

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